

SOME REMARKS ABOUT THE NOVEL “IMAM MOTURUDIY” LUQMAN BORIKHAN

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The ancient city is a sacred place that has produced many great scholars over the centuries. Among them, a famous representative of theology, theology and tafsir, Imam Abu Mansur Moturudiy, occupies a special place. It is no coincidence that his rich scientific heritage is considered the basis of Islamic thought, a scientific approach against dogmatism, not only in the medieval Muslim world, but also today. The signing of the Decree “On the Wide Celebration of the 1150th Anniversary of the Birth of the Famous Thinker and Theologian Imam Abu Mansur Moturidi” by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev is also worthy of great attention as an expression of the harmony of science, religion and spirituality [1].

Literature, based on its historical memory and strong cultural foundation, plays an important role in the spiritual upliftment of every nation. The rich traditions of Uzbek literature, including works of art aimed at highlighting the lives and activities of historical figures, are of particular importance in this direction. Historical novels serve as an incomparable tool for artistic observation of the past, revealing historical figures with new approaches, and instilling their spiritual heritage into the consciousness of the people. The novel “Imam Moturidi”, created by Luqman Borikhan through such a historical-artistic approach, also stands out in contemporary literature with its unique style and philosophical connotation.

The embodiment of such spiritual values as national identity, faith, thought, and patience in the personification of historical figures demonstrates the writer's writing skills, devotion to historical truth, and most importantly, originality in the art of creating an artistic image. In the novel "Imam Moturidiy", the author not only captured the life and scientific activities of the great scholar, but also depicted the environment around him, the spirit of the era, the contradictions of the time, ideological struggles, issues of religion and worldview based on deep artistic perception. In particular, through the inner experiences of the heroes of the novel, psychological portraits, and their contrasting characters, the writer demonstrated his deep artistic analysis and character creation skills.

In Uzbek literature, there is a widespread tendency to address historical themes, understand the past, and reflect the spirit of the present through its artistic interpretation. As one of the bright examples of this trend, the novel "Imam Moturidiy" by Luqman Borikhan can be highlighted. The work illuminates the life, scientific heritage and times of Imam Moturidiy, who lived selflessly in the path of sacred knowledge, through artistic images. First of all, it is related to the place and legacy of Imam Moturidiy in Islamic science, and secondly, it is also significant in that it serves to form historical consciousness in today's young generation through artistic interpretation of the lives of such historical personalities. In this regard, the role of literature, especially works in the historical novel genre, is incomparable. The novel "Imam Moturidiy" can serve as an important source in this spiritual and educational process.

Therefore, the analysis of the images created on the basis of this novel, their place in society, and the study of the level of artistic truth have become a necessity not only for literary criticism, but also for propagators of spirituality.

In today's era of globalization, the innovations and changes taking place in the social life of mankind are reflected in literary literature, and the era itself demands that it should also serve to raise the spirituality of that society. Works from the treasury of world literature, where high universal ideas are propagated, not only cultivate the reader's artistic taste, but also help to raise his worldview and artistic thinking. Based on this, the study of the aspects of the artistic talent of the skilled writers who wrote such works is also considered one of the urgent issues facing the science of literary criticism. There are various manifestations of artistry in world literary criticism, and the scope of the image of the literary text, the author's attitude, the selection of the world of images and the poetic perception of the problem posed through them, as well as the aesthetic ideal, worldview, problems of interpretation, in general, the specific aspects of the writer's artistic skill are being studied on the example of the creative product he created. It is important to conduct scientific research based on the development of traditions, such as the interpretation of spiritual suffering in the works of a particular writer written in different years and in a unique style, the creation of a unique image in the landscape of the period, character and typical circumstances, and the problematic of the hero in a work of art.

One of the creators who stands out in the history of Uzbek literature with his unique voice, unique style and deep philosophical observations is Luqman Borikhan. His works, especially his artistic examples in the genres of short stories, stories and novels, marked a new stage in Uzbek prose. The life and work of the writer are studied with great interest not only by literary critics, but also by young creators and book lovers. Luqman Borikhan left his mark on literature through his life experience, observation and images in the folk spirit. His works deeply cover the spirit of the times, human values, social inequality, moral criteria, rural life, family and personality issues. These aspects show Luqman Borikhan as a great writer who works in literature on the basis of realism and philosophical generalization. Therefore, analyzing his works, studying the stages of his formation as a writer, and analyzing his life and creative path are of great scientific and practical importance today.

Luqman Borikhan takes a literary approach to history, that is, he presents historical facts in the form of a novel and analyzes them artistically. His heroes are real historical figures, through whom the reader feels the atmosphere of the historical period. This style is a unique aspect of the writer's work. This approach is also clearly visible in the novel "Imam Maturidi". Through the novel, he takes the reader to the atmosphere of Transoxiana in the 9th-10th centuries. The writer widely used historical sources, religious books, hadith and exegetical works to create the image of historical figures. This indicates how deep his research was. For example, when writing about the life of Imam Maturidi, he relies on sources such as "Al-Fiqh al-Akbar", "Kitab at-Tawhid", "Sharh al-Usul". Thus, the writer is based not only on imagination, but also on concrete evidence when creating the image of a historical figure.

Luqman Borikhan encourages the people not to forget their past and to understand national pride through historical themes. This reveals the creative intention of the writer. He is not only a writer, but also a propagator of spirituality. The novel "Imam Moturidiy" in particular plays an important role in this regard. Because it reflects not only one historical figure, but also an entire era, thought, and scientific school. Luqman Borikhan's main reason for writing

historical novels is to learn lessons from history and instill it in the minds of the people. At the same time, he also draws attention to modern problems through historical images. Because every historical figure and every historical event teaches important lessons for the modern reader. This approach reflects the writer's philosophical views.

“His work embodies the depth of thought, spiritual search and devotion to historical truth. That is why the works of Luqman Borikhan arouse great interest among readers. Especially works such as “Imam Moturidiy” serve to increase religious and spiritual knowledge. By writing this work, the writer expressed his spiritual views, religious level and love for his people. The writer also pays special attention to the literary language in his works. He writes in a simple but deeply meaningful style. This ensures easy acceptance by the reader. Such a methodological approach also confirms that the writer is a talented creator” [2, p. 45].

The complexity of writing historical novels is that the writer must rely on history, literature and philosophy at the same time. Luqman Borikhan also achieved success in this regard [3, p. 56]. He was able to combine all three areas into a single whole. It is these aspects that distinguish his novels from others. Each historical work written by Luqman Borikhan serves as a textbook. Because it contains history, enlightenment, morality, and lessons. This novel by the writer closely introduces the reader to the life and work of the great thinker, and its spiritual perfection has an impact on the reader's thinking: " - Hazrat, we were the ones who cooked it, please, spare a spoonful of our blood, - the official tried his best in a soft voice, - do not pray for us. - Okay, let it be as you wish, stay where you are, my friend, - said the Hazrat, nodding, - for what purpose are you looking for Abu Mansur? The official straightened up and put his hand on his chest. - You know, three days ago a new governor was appointed from Bukhara to Samarkand. Our governor Khalid Khalaj invites you to the Qala-i Qasr" [4, p.25]. In these interpretations, it is possible to understand that Abu Mansur's generosity was the reason for inviting him. The unique poetic characteristics of the lines in the novel are evidence of their skillful interpretation and the author's skill in creating artistic characters.

It is especially important to educate the younger generation through such works [5, p.74]. That is why the writer's work, especially his historical novels, is of great importance today. His historical works are also highly appreciated. Uzbek literary criticism evaluates Luqmon Borikhan's historical novels as an expression of modern historical thinking. This is a sign of high attention paid to the writer's creative work [6,p.44].

In general, this novel by the talented writer Luqmon Borikhan, like his other works, is distinguished by its artistic interpretation of our past, its bright, fleeting moments.

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